

Study of L-Proline Complexes of Bivalent Metal Ions

K. K. Girdhar, K. K. Vaid and P. S. Relan

The formation of Bivalent Metal Ions-complexes with L-Proline have been studied by *pH* method. The formation constants of the complexes have been determined by Irving and Rossotti method. The stability constants are in the order $Cd < Co < Ni < UO_2 < CU > Zn$. They obey Irving-Williams and Mellor and Maley order. The predominating form of the metal complexes in solution is 1 : 1 combination of the metal ion and amino acid.

The study of metal amino complexes is important as it gives an insight of the linkage involved in metal protein interaction. The linkage involved can be studied by an equilibria between the metal ions and amino acids¹. In the present investigation the stability of bivalent metal cations have been studied potentiometrically by Irving and Rossotti² method. The linkage between metal ions and ligand has been interpreted.

EXPERIMENTAL AND DISCUSSION

The *pH* was recorded on a *pH* meter "ELICO LI-10" which reads upto an accuracy of 0.1. All measurements were made in a thermostat at $20^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. All metal salts used were nitrates except uranyl, in which case its acetate was taken.

The formation constants were obtained from the data obtained by solutions containing (I) metal salt solution (0.004*M*) + L-Proline (0.005*M*) + Hydrochloric acid (0.0004*M*), (II) L-Proline (0.005*M*) + Hydrochloric acid (0.0004*M*) and (III) Hydrochloric acid (0.0004*M*) maintained at a constant volume of 20 mls. in each case, against standard potassium hydroxide (0.05*M*). The ionic strength was maintained constant at 0.1*M* with potassium chloride.

The proton-ligand stability constants calculated by the relationship $\log PK_nH = B + \log n^{-A}/1 - n^{-A}$ are 10.48 and 2.02. The values are quite in agreement with the values already reported in literature³. The values of $\log k_1$ was obtained at $n^- = 0.5$ by drawing graphs between n^- versus *pA*. The values of $\log k_2$ could not be obtained due to the predominating (1 : 1) form of the metal complexes. The data obtained is reported in Table I.

1. Stability constants of metal ion complexes, special publication No. 17, Section II, Organic Ligands (The Chemical Society, London) 1964.
2. H. Irving and H. S. Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
3. Harry Kroll, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 2034.

The order of stability is $\text{Cd} < \text{Co} < \text{Ni} < \text{UO}_2 < \text{Cu} > \text{Zn}$ as represented by the data in Table I. It is in quite agreement with the order of stability of Irving and Williams⁴ and Mellor and Maley⁵.

TABLE I

Stability constants of Bivalent cations

$[pK_1^H(\text{COOH}) \text{ of L-Proline} = 2.02; pK_2^H(\text{NH}_3^+) \text{ of L-Proline} = 10.48]$

Metal Ion	$\log k_1$
Cadmium	4.40
Cobalt	4.89
Zinc	5.36
Nickel	5.46
Uranyl	7.75
Copper	8.37

L-proline is an α -amino acid. The binding of bivalent cations is stronger in proline compared with glycine³, another α -amino acid. The stability of the complex is related to the acidity of the dissociating ammonium group which is more in case of proline. The pK_1^H for L-proline is one unit higher than glycine. Hence the metal ions are more firmly bound by a more basic α -amino group.

Thanks are due to Dr. K. G. Narayan, Soil Microbiologist and Head of Chemistry and Biochemistry Department, Haryana Agricultural University, Hissar for providing necessary facilities.

Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry,
Haryana Agricultural University,
Hissar (Haryana).

Received January 24, 1970

4. H. Irving and R. J. P. Williams, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.
5. D. P. Mellor, and L. Maley, *Nature*, London, 1947, **159**, 370.